

TRAVEL AND TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN JAPAN.

Bakhrillaeva Marjona

Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14059620>

Abstract. The current research aims at analysing travel and tourism development in Japan using qualitative descriptive approach on the basis of Travel and Tourism Development Index(TTDI) provided by World Economic Forum. The study relies on data accumulated from existing literature and resources in order to thoroughly examine each indicator of TTDI framework. Findings explore that Japan has experienced a remarkable development, making the destination a premier location for international travelers.

Key words: travel, tourism, development, Japan, TTDI, WEF.

Introduction. Travel and tourism are essential components of today's thriving global society. WTTC reported that in 2023 travel and tourism sector contributed 9.1% to the global GDP. Being one of the great industrial field, tourism drives economic growth, creates employment opportunities and promotes social development at the same time. The concept of travel and tourism development has been given main emphasis in majority of tourism studies for a long period of time and it still holds key significance in tourism research area. Tourism is regarded as having a dynamic nature like any other complex human activity, all of which are capable of changing over time (Butler, 1997), triggering economic growth and becoming an important target for most governments (Lee, Chang 2008). In Japan, tourism has gradually become a key activity reinforcing the country's economy since 2000 (Horita,2020). From 2011 to 2015, Japan's inbound tourism grew by 33 % per year, among fastest rates in the world (André et al.,2016). The country hosted 32 million inbound visitors in 2019, tourists spent \$43.6 billion expenditure according to the Japan times' report. The most popular cities in Japan for international travelers are Tokyo and Osaka, in 2023, Tokyo ranked 4th among the world's most popular cities and Osaka was in 16th (worlddata.info). The World Economic Forum (WEF)'s Travel and Tourism Development Index (TTDI) ranked Japan first in the development index in 2021 due to the speed with which travel and tourism industry has recovered from the devastation caused by the pandemic. This study examines travel and tourism development in Japan on the basis of TTDI framework provided by WEF, exploring each indicator relying on the secondary data accumulated from existing sources.

Data and sources.

Table 1. Travel and Tourism Development Index framework. Source: The World Economic Forum.

Enabling environment.

Business environment. Tourism business is regarded as one of Japan’s cultural innovations. The first technique they use is creating “cultural identity” of a tourist attraction that makes the spot stand aside from others. Another method is designing mascots for each tourist attraction as an ambassador for tourism and as a souvenir product in several sources. In order to prosper their tourism business, japanese use technology and communication through tourist assistance centers, QR code translators and many other advancements (Siam Commercial Bank).

Table 2. Top seven tourism companies in Japan.

WAmazing	Application services offered to foreign tourists
Scheme verge, inc	A smart city start up aiming revolutionize urban development
Biodata bank	New E-health solution with core body temperature monitoring
Gym in Japan	Gym searching&reservation web service in Tokyo
Acomo, Inc	Innovating in the travel industry
Mona JP	IoT&SaaS enables businesses to build DApps to deliver real world impact
Aquabit spirals	Hyperlink of things Merges Physical with digital in contactless smart city.

Source: www.F6S.com

Safety and security.

Japan is ranked with very low crime rate, and the country is very safe for visitors. However, Japan National Tourism Organisation suggest travelers to be aware of their surroundings. Even if a traveler victims form of violence or crime, they are asked to head to a local koban - the small police boxes dotted throughout Japanese neighborhoods.

Health and hygiene.

In June 2020, there was a survey carried out in 12 countries where 6,266 people with international travel experience asked “which country or region do you want to go visit after the coronavirus subsides? Japan was chosen by 46% of respondents where hygiene level in the country was mostly valued. (japanforward.com)

Human resource and labour market.

In 2021, the influence of tourism on employment rate in Japan indicated 1.56 tourism industry as an integral part labour market in the country (statista.com).

ICT readiness. ICT has become an integral part of travel and tourism sector in Japan. From planning itineraries to booking processes, ICT holds focal role in implementing all the procedures. According to Japanese national tour organization, the country has been synonymous with technology since 1960s. The country represents many smart cities with latest technology advancements for tech-lover travelers.

Travel and tourism policy and enabling conditions.

Prioritization of tourism and International openness. In 2021, Japan scored the top in TTDI ranking, but in prioritization of tourism ranking it took 42nd position probably due to the pandemic border closures. However, Japan has reopened to

the world after two years of setback, with an accessibility of entering to the country without visa requirements for the citizens of 68 countries.

Infrastructure.

Air transport infrastructure. Japan is said to have strong air transport infrastructure (statista.com) with more than 100 airports, including 28 major and 54 regional airports. They are controlled by national or regional authorities, except for four-company international airports.

Ground and port infrastructure. Since 1999, an e-system for port related procedures has been operated in Japan. A single window system became available that operates facilities related to import/export of cargo and entry/exit of the vessels according to ports and harbours bureau in the country.

Tourism services infrastructure. Travel and tourism infrastructure is known for being technology-advanced, clean, sustainable and punctual in Japan. Particularly, Shinkansen bullet train is a high speed rail network in the destination providing comfortable environment for its passengers. (Japan Educational Travel).

Travel and tourism demand drivers

Natural resources	12 natural wonders
Cultural resources	20 cultural heritage sites

Travel and Tourism sustainability.

Japanese people are now well aware of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). According to the consumer survey of 1,400 respondents throughout Japan, 86% of people said that they were aware, and understood the detail, of the SDGs. This survey has been conducted annually for the past four years, and awareness has increased sixfold since the first survey in 2018.

Results and discussion.

The context of the research reveal that Japan has been through many development stages until it came to the 1st level in TTDI ranking. Each of the indicators showed different phases of improvement. Especially, it is worth noting that incorporating tourism businesses with technology advancements for promoting various applications ensuring industry's growth and competitiveness. By making tourism services easily accessible for the visitors applying latest technology opportunities helps to attract more visitors and

increase satisfaction levels in the destination. When traveling, traveler not only considers travel and tourism service quality, but also check overall condition of a country of interest. Is it safe and free from social, environmental and other threats? Thus, while planning to attract more tourists to the country safety and security should be given high priority As an example of Japan, a country which is known for its safe and secure atmosphere. Health and hygiene has always been crucial part of Japanese tourism development, making the country the most optimal destination for health tourism. Many people are employed by tourism industry in Japan contributing to the total economic and industrial growth rates. Japanese infrastructure development leading to majority visitors choose the country as the best tourism destination, which helps to increase satisfaction levels in travel and tourism sector. Sustainability, a common term integrated with the development of the tourism destinations representing a very good levels of awareness and implementation.

Conclusion.

This research paper analyzed travel and tourism development in Japan according to the indicators of TTDI index provided by World Economic Forum. As the country topped the list in development in 2021 in travel and tourism sector, the author found researching this topic worthwhile aiming to contribute to the future studies. Japanese development experience can be valuable framework for other countries to shape their development pathways in travel and tourism industry.

References:

1. World Economic Forum
2. World Travel and Tourism Organisation
3. Richard W. Butler Emeritus Professor (2009) Tourism Destination Development: Cycles and Forces, Myths and Realities, Tourism Recreation Research, 34:3, 247-254, DOI: 10.1080/02508281.2009.11081600
4. Chien-Chiang Lee, Chun-Ping Chang (2008) Tourism management: Tourism development and economic growth: A closer look at panels
5. André Andonian Managing Partner, Japan, Tasuku Kuwabara , Partner, Japan, Naomi Yamakawa Expert Associate Partner, Japan, Ryo Ishida Consultant, Japan: The future of Japan's tourism: Path for sustainable growth towards 2020
6. worlddata.unfo
7. Siam Commercial Bank website
8. Japan National Tourism Organisation
9. www.F6S.com

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

10.japanforward.com

11.statista.com

12.Japan educational travel

13.Timeout.com

